

Table 1. Summary of remote sensing and bat acoustic surveys conducted by ship in the Mid-Atlantic.

Source	Coverage	Distance from land (km)	Number of detectors	Height (m)	Survey dates	Number of nights	Total passes	Overall rate ^a
Geo-Marine 2010	Barge moved among grid cells off New	0 - 20	n/a ^b		03/24/08-05/11/08, 10/1/08-10/19/08, 05/11/09-05/12/09	56	45	0.80
Sjollema et al. 2014	Five research and fishing vessels sailed routes off New Jersey and Delmarva Peninsula	1.2 - 166.0	10 (2 per vessel)	1.8 - 12.2	03/11/09-10/31/09, 04/21/10-08/26/10	86	166	1.93
Peterson et al. 2016	NOAA research vessel sailed routes from coastal Massachusetts to North Carolina	5.26 - 129.6	1	10	08/15/14-09/29/14	52	35	0.67
Craven et al. 2020	Research vessel sailed routes within BOEM ^c Renewable Energy Lease Area OCS-A 0512 off New Jersey	22.2 - 44.4	1	23	05/29/18-12/02/18	188	584	3.10

^a passes/detector-night

^b acoustic detectors not used. A thermal camera paired with a vertically pointed radar recorded signatures of foraging bats.

^c BOEM = Bureau of Ocean Energy Management